

Cross-cultural adaptation and validation of a modified version of ARB-VFQ-25 in Iraq

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Abstract

This study aimed to validate a modified Arabic version (mARB-VFQ-25) for Iraqi patients with diabetic maculopathies. Although an Arabic mARB-VFQ-25 exists, it has not yet been validated in Iraq. The adaptation process involved two steps: first, modifying the original to reduce length and remove redundancies, with revisions by an ophthalmologist and a clinical pharmacist for cultural relevance; second, assessing its psychometric properties. Participants diagnosed with diabetic maculopathies were interviewed face-to-face. On average, the questionnaire took approximately 9 minutes and 26 seconds to complete. Internal consistency was acceptable, with Cronbach's alpha coefficients above 0.4 for most subscales, except for "Ocular pain" (0.285) and "Dependency" (-0.100). The adapted tool is easy to administer, reliable, and time-efficient for evaluating vision-related quality of life among Iraqi patients. In conclusion, the mARB-VFQ-25 is a valid, culturally sensitive, and practical instrument for clinical and research use within this population.

Keywords

quality of life, diabetic retinopathy, validation studies, cross-cultural comparison, Arabic

Introduction

Assessment of visual function plays a significant role in measuring quality of life (QoL). It is a valuable tool for evaluating patients with ophthalmological conditions and their treatment, alongside other assessments such as visual field and visual acuity (van Nispen 2020; Oshima 2021; Magakwe 2024). Diabetes mellitus (DM) negatively impacts vision and QoL, which warrants special attention (Al-Any 2016). However, the visual effects of DM are less studied compared to its neuropathy (Hadi 2020; Mohammad 2022; Najim 2024b) and nephropathy (Majeed 2024; Najim 2024a, b). While tests such as visual acuity and visual field are essential, they only offer a superficial understanding of how visual impairments affect

daily life (Anderson et al. 2023). There is a notable lack of tools to measure the subjective and complex aspects of vision-related QoL (Magakwe et al. 2024). Conventional assessments do not address broader implications such as emotional well-being, social participation, and overall functionality, especially in diabetic patients. The gap is evident: current methods inadequately examine the visual consequences of DM and fail to connect objective findings with patients' perceptions (Hamid et al. 2018). This underscores the need for a specialized, visually oriented QoL instrument that integrates clinical metrics and patient-reported outcomes.

In 1996, the National Eye Institute developed the NEI-VFQ-51, a 51-item instrument with 13 subscales to assess vision-related QoL, tested on patients with ophthalmic

conditions (Mangione 1998; Abdelfattah 2014). A shorter 25-item version, mARB-VFQ-25, was introduced in 2000, retaining 12 subscales and similar psychometric properties, offering greater convenience (Mangione 1999, 2001). In Egypt, an Arabic version was created in 2014 to overcome language barriers and improve data reliability (Abdelfattah 2014). This questionnaire has been translated and validated in numerous languages, including Italian, French, Japanese, Turkish, Spanish, Portuguese, Greek, Chinese, Persian, Danish, German, Bahasa Malaysia, and Croatian, among others. It has also been adapted for local Arabic dialects in Morocco and Tunisia (Kosnia 2021). The ARB-VFQ-25 has been used across Arab countries such as Tunisia, Jordan, Egypt, and Oman, and among Syrian patients in non-Arabic-speaking countries, to assess vision-related QoL in various conditions (Knani 2017; Almhdawi 2020; Hammad 2020; Mohamed 2022; Bal 2018). Additionally, a very short version, VFQ-3007, contains seven items, three of which are administered to the patient (Visser 2020).

No validation studies of the ARB-VFQ-25 have been conducted in Iraq. Many items are outdated and not culturally aligned with Iraqi contexts. Creating an Iraqi Arabic version is challenging due to regional dialect variations, although most Iraqis understand Standard Arabic, which might be more suitable (Alaa' Al-Bazzaz 2020). This study aims to validate a modified Iraqi Arabic version of the NEI-Visual Function Questionnaire (mARB-VFQ-25) and adapt it culturally for the Iraqi population.

Methods

Study design and settings

This was a cross-sectional study involving 31 DM patients with diabetic maculopathies. Patients were recruited from the Department of Ophthalmology of Ghazi Al-Hariri Surgical Hospital, Baghdad Medical City, between 1 July 2024, and 1 December 2024. Those who presented for visual consultations or follow-up appointments and met the eligibility criteria were included. All investigations adhered to the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki, informed written

consent was obtained from all participants, and Institutional Review Board approval was secured for the study. The study was prepared following the STROBE guidelines for reporting observational studies (Cuschieri 2019).

Eligibility criteria

Patients included in this study were aged ≥ 40 years with diabetic maculopathies, diagnosed according to fundus ophthalmoscopy and optical coherence tomography (OCT) (Sikorski et al. 2013). Patients with hearing problems or those who failed to respond to questions were excluded. The questionnaire had to be administered face-to-face, as most patients suffered from vision problems and had limited reading ability.

Ethical considerations

This study was reviewed and approved by the Research Ethical Committee of the College of Pharmacy, Mustansiriyah University (approval number: 73; reference number: 173; date: 5 June 2024).

Development of the modified Arabic version

The ARB-VFQ-25 was modified to create a new version, termed mARB-VFQ-25, as shown in Table 1. The ARB-VFQ-25 includes 25 items across 12 domains to assess vision-related quality of life (QoL), as detailed in Table 2. Responses to each item are converted to a scale ranging from 0 to 100, with 100 representing the best QoL and 0 the worst.

After the revision of ARB-VFQ-25, some questions were merged, others were omitted, and some were rephrased to be more modern and compatible with Iraqi culture. Following these modifications and revisions, a new questionnaire, mARB-VFQ-25, was designed for testing. All optional items were assigned the letter "A" for further distinction.

Tables 1, 3 present the list of items in mARB-VFQ-25 and a comparison with the previous ARB-VFQ-25 (see Suppl. material 1 for the final version of ARB-VFQ-25).

Table 1. Modifications applied to ARB-VFQ-25.

Item	Suggestions
Item 5	As newspapers are no longer widely used or read, the statement was changed to ask about reading from books, texts on phones, bills, medication boxes, or any legal documents, including identification cards.
Item 14	As it is not familiar to Iraqis to watch movies in cinemas or plays in theaters, the statement was modified to include attending public activities and festivals and adding "football games" to explain sports events.
Item A1	It was removed, as it repeats the intent of "item 1".
Item A2	It was removed, as it repeats the intent of "item 2".
Item A3	It was merged into "item 5".
Item A4	It was merged into "item 5".
Item A7	It was merged into "item 14".
Item A8	It was merged into "item 14".
Item A12	It was merged into "item 3".
Item A13	It was merged into "item 24".

Table 2. List of items in ARB-VFQ-25 before modification.

Subscales	Items	Number of items	Number of optional items and their details [#]
General health	1, A1	2	1 (item A1)
General vision	2, A2	2	1 (item A2)
Well-being/distress (mental health)	3, 21, 22, 25, A12	5	1 (item A12)
Ocular pain	4, 19	2	0
Near vision issues	5, 6, 7, A3, A4, A5	6	3 (items A3, A4, and A5)
Distance vision issues	8, 9, 14, A6, A7, A8	6	3 (items A6, A7, and A8)
Peripheral vision	10	1	0
Social function	11, 13, A9	3	1 (item A9)
Color vision	12	1	0
Driving	15 (15a, 15b, 15c), 16 (16a*)	2 (with sub-questions)	0
Role limitation	17, 18, A11a, A11b	4	2 (items A11a and A11b)
Dependency	20, 23, 24, A13	4	1 (item A13)

* Item 16a was listed as item A10 in previous versions. [#] All items that are not optional are considered core.

Table 3. List of subscales and items after modifications to mARB-VFQ-25.

Subscales	Items	Number of items	Number of optional items and their details [#]
General health	1	1	0
General vision	2	1	0
Well-being/distress (mental health)	3, 21, 22, 25	4	0
Ocular pain	4, 19	2	0
Near vision issues	5, 6, 7, A5	4	1 (item A5)
Distance vision issues	8, 9, 14, A6	4	1 (item A6)
Peripheral vision	10	1	0
Social function	11, 13, A9	3	1 (item A9)
Color vision	12	1	0
Driving	15 (15a, 15b, 15c), 16 (16a*)	2 (with sub-questions)	0
Role limitation	17, 18, A11a, A11b	4	2 (items A11a and A11b)
Dependency	20, 23, 24	3	0

[#] All items that are not optional are core.

Study of the feasibility and reliability of mARB-VFQ-25

To assess the feasibility, reliability, and validity of the mARB-VFQ-25, the researchers administered it face-to-face to 31 patients with diabetic maculopathies who were eligible for the study. The administration time was recorded to evaluate feasibility. Items were analyzed to determine the percentage of missing responses and to assess whether the questionnaire was suitable and easy to apply to the target population.

Reliability was evaluated using internal consistency (IC) correlations for each subscale. The acceptable range for Cronbach's alpha is 0.70 to 0.90. Additionally, the item-scale correlation coefficient was calculated to assess scale homogeneity, with coefficients above 0.40 considered acceptable.

Sample size calculation

The G-power program version 3.1 was used to calculate the sample size (post hoc power analysis), with 80% power, a 0.05 alpha level, an effect size of 0.27, a linear regression model with 25 predictors, and a total sample size of 31 (Festing 2006; Faul et al. 2007).

Statistical analysis

Descriptive statistics included the mean (standard deviation) for continuous variables and frequency (percentage) for categorical variables. IC was tested using Cronbach's alpha coefficient, which ranges between 0 and 1. The closer its value is to 1, the more homogeneous all the elements are. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient is considered good above 0.7 (Landis 1977). For statistical analyses, GraphPad Prism version 10.4.1 was used.

Results

The study included 31 DM patients. The mean age was 62.3 ± 12.0 years; 21 were male (67.74%) and 10 were female (32.26%). Twenty-six patients had hypertension (83.87%), while six patients had a history of stroke, myocardial infarction, or other thrombotic conditions (19.35%).

Regarding feasibility, the analysis of mARB-VFQ-25 items showed no missing answers, except for item 5 (41.9%) and the driving subscale items 15 and 16 (64.5%), as shown in Table 4.

The item–scale correlation coefficients were generally above 0.4 (Abdelfattah 2014). However, the “Dependency” and “Ocular pain” subscales had correlations below 0.40, as shown in Table 5. The low correlation for the “Ocular pain” subscale may be due to the nature of the condition studied, since pain is not the primary symptom.

As shown in Table 6, all subscales demonstrated acceptable reliability in both the short version with 25 questions and the full version with optional questions (30 questions), as assessed by the Cronbach alpha test.

As shown in Fig. 1, all subscales demonstrated an acceptable correlation with the composite score, with a correlation coefficient above 0.4 for all subscales.

Table 4. Descriptive data of respondents’ scores according to their answers to mARB-VFQ-25.

Subscale	Value
General health [#]	25.00 (0.0–50.0)
General Vision [§]	49.03 ± 19.21
Peripheral vision [§]	82.26 ± 27.53
Color vision [§]	92.74 ± 17.31
Near vision [§]	70.23 ± 22.09
Distance vision [§]	79.23 ± 23.96
Social function [§]	88.17 ± 17.45
driving, median [#]	66.67 (0–100)
role limitation [#]	50.00 (25.00–68.75)
Ocular pain [§]	64.92 ± 19.48
Dependency [§]	66.67 (50.0–75.0)
Well-being/distress [#]	31.25 (12.50–68.75)
Composite score [§]	63.84 ± 18.39

[#] median (interquartile range), [§] mean ± standard deviation.

Table 5. Item–scale correlation coefficients of ARB-VFQ-25.

Subscale	Item–scale correlation [#]
General health	0.695
General vision	0.515
Peripheral vision	0.572
Color vision	0.785
Near vision	0.842
Distance vision	0.787
Social function	0.794
Driving	0.472
Role limitation	0.608
Ocular pain	0.285
Dependency	-0.100
Well-being/distress	0.497
Composite score	0.978

[#] Measured by the Cronbach alpha.

Discussion

This study presents mARB-VFQ-25, which is adapted to the Iraqi context and has satisfactory psychometric properties in terms of internal consistency and feasibility. Some modifications were made to items 5 and 14 to match the Iraqi cultural context and recent cultural changes.

Since newspapers are no longer widely used, item 5 was changed to include reading from books, texts on phones, bills, medication boxes, legal documents, and ID cards. Items A3 and A4 were merged into this item for

Table 6. Internal reliability (convergent validity) of ARB-VFQ (25- and 30-question versions).

Subscale	Cronbach alpha	
	Without optional items	With optional items
General Health	NA	NA
General vision	NA	NA
Ocular pain	0.744	0.744
Near vision	0.655	0.680
Distance activities	0.919	0.910
Social functioning	0.864	0.860
Mental health	0.928	0.928
Role difficulties	0.988	0.842
Dependency	0.835	0.835
Driving	0.522	0.522
Color vision	NA	NA
Peripheral vision	NA	NA

NA: not applicable (since these subscales contain only one item, the Cronbach alpha value cannot be calculated).

comprehensiveness. Regarding item 14, as Iraqis rarely watch movies in cinemas or attend plays, the statement was modified to include attending public activities and festivals, with “football games” added for sports events. Other minor modifications were also made. According to guidelines, these changes are minor and maintain the questionnaire’s comparability across cultures and nationalities (Beaton 2000).

The face-to-face administration of the questionnaire took an average of 9 minutes and 26 seconds (± 3 minutes 11 seconds), which was shorter than the original Arabic version (ARB-VFQ-25), the English version, and many other foreign editions (Rossi 2003; Nordmann 2004; Suzukamo 2005; Toprak 2005; Baker 2006; Labiris 2008; Simão 2008; Chan 2009; Lin 2010; Asgari 2011; Sørensen et al. 2011; Nickels 2017; Lešin Gačina 2021; Thevi 2021). Some versions took longer, such as the French version, which required 20–30 minutes when administered by phone (Nordmann 2004). The item analysis showed a very low rate of missing responses, except for a few items such as the driving subscale (items 15 and 16), which had a missing rate of 64.5%. Most respondents were elderly patients who either never drove or had stopped driving due to age. Since the study was conducted in a government hospital, most patients belonged to middle- or low-income groups. This trend was also observed in other translations from Egypt (Abdelfattah 2014), Tunisia (Ksaa 2021), China (Chan 2009), and Malaysia (Thevi 2021), where participants generally had limited access to personal vehicles. Lloyd et al. (2013) combined driving with another domain, and the driving items were excluded in the short version VFQ-30o7 (Visser 2020). Nonetheless, the driving subscale showed acceptable item–scale correlation and reliability.

It is worth noting that the low item–scale correlation with the “Ocular pain” subscale may be due to the nature of the condition studied, as pain is not a main symptom. With the exception of the “Dependency” subscale, all other subscales showed acceptable to optimal Cronbach alpha results. In addition, all subscales demonstrated an acceptable correlation with the composite score, indicating that the items are reliable.

Figure 1. Correlation matrix of the total composite score with its subscales (reliability).

The Dependency subscale showed a negative Cronbach alpha (-0.100), indicating serious reliability problems, unlike the other subscales, which performed well. Scoring errors were ruled out, suggesting the issue stems from conceptual inconsistency among items—possibly measuring divergent aspects of dependency or even opposing traits. The negative value implies that the dependency items were not functioning together as intended, likely due to a problematic item or construct definition. The small number of items in the subscale may have amplified instability, but the negative inter-item covariance points to a deeper lack of coherence. This undermines construct validity, making any results based on the subscale unreliable and preliminary. As Streiner (2003) explains, if items were correctly scored yet still produce a negative alpha, it “points to problems in the original construction of the scale” (Streiner 2003).

Regarding the study’s limitations, all participants had diabetic maculopathies and were recruited from the Department of Ophthalmology in a single hospital. Although the hospital is a referral center for ophthalmology, including a larger number of patients and recruiting individuals with other ophthalmologic conditions would provide broader representation and may help account for age and other characteristics that could affect responses.

Conclusion

Our results suggest that mARB-VFQ-25 is a valid and reliable tool for assessing vision-related QoL. It is important to establish such a valuable instrument for evaluating vision-related QoL among Iraqi adult patients. Accordingly, further studies on Iraqi and other Arabic patients with miscellaneous eye conditions are required to investigate the influence of vision quality on patients’ well-being and social functioning.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors’ representatives: This research study has been reviewed and approved by the Research Ethical Committee of the College of Pharmacy, Mustansiriyah University (Approval number: 73, reference number: 173, date: 5 June 2024).

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

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Supplementary material 1

Final version of ARB-VFQ-25

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